

ColaboFlow - An AI augmented workflow platform for "solidifying" the hybrid research processes into executable workflows

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Keywords: Workflows, solidification, AI augmentation, BPMN, research reproducibility, DH research

Abstract: In this paper, we promote and evaluate the usage of workflows in digital humanities (DH) as a supporter of reproducible research. We present ColaboFlow, a generic workflow framework that supports both visual and descriptive mechanisms for expressing and executing workflows. ColaboFlow is a generic framework, which can support various research scenarios. However, to put it in the context of DH research, we present it in two specific DH contexts. First, we present it through Bukvik, a specialized instance of ColaboFlow that supports common DH research workflows addressing distant reading, stylometry, and parallel multilingual corpora. Secondly, we bring it to LitTerra, a DH hybrid-reading platform that supports running workflows in a hybrid reading context, especially multilingual parallel reading. Through the practical context of LitTerra and Bukvik, we introduce DH literary scholars to the possibilities and benefits of conducting their research through workflows. We explore, further, the requirements ColaboFlow, as a workflow framework, needs to provide both from the perspective of reproducible DH research and from the perspective of digitalization of research processes. We argue that workflows are inherent enablers of reproducible research. We additionally argue their benefit of keeping the human-in-the-loop approach, especially in the new era of AI augmentation where human-in-the-loop converges from a norm to an exception in most scenarios. We propose the process of "solidification". This AI augmented methodology helps a researcher to transform their creative research process (or work) from descriptive and tacit into solid, executable, and reproducible workflows. By externalizing its outcome into visual and comprehensive workflows, the methodology enables transparent AI inherently. Even with transparency in mind and aiming for the keeping *human-in-the-loop* approach, this evidently needed augmentation of the research process introduces, in the era of human+AI symbiotic research, a new risk of disengaging human participants from creative thinking and decision-making. Therefore, we argue that instead of keeping human *in* the loop, whereby the human tends to become a passive observer of the AI's decisions and actions, we should keep human *on* the loop. We introduce additional responsible AI-enabled *gate-keeping* and evaluation mechanisms to counterbalance the risks. With this, we promote and enable keeping the *human-on-the-loop* approach in the DH research and creative processes. This is a more advanced and beneficial approach to human+AI symbiotic research, which proactively engages participants in critical and creative thinking and decision-making. The presented approach helps keep human on the loop; documents (digitizes) and clarifies the creative process and work; and ensures the transparency of the created workflows. Additionally, it enables ongoing collaborative and AI interventions on the workflows and their reproducible execution in distributed environments. Finally, we evaluate the solidification process and the ColaboFlow framework through both human-provided data and partially synthetic data generated from the human-provided data.

1 INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we present the ColaboFlow framework as an approach for practicing workflows in research, primarily demonstrating it in the context of DH. We introduce workflows, explain how they work and their specific implementation and usage in the

ColaboFlow framework. We argue why workflows matter for reproducible research and how they can help digitize the research process. We introduce an AI-augmented "solidification" methodology for expressing research work through solid, executable, and reproducible workflows. While AI helps and boosts researchers' capacity, it hinders their critical thinking,

creativity and decision making. Therefore, we need to introduce countermeasures to compensate for the negative effects of the augmentation.

With the rise of AI models that, in specialized working domains, approaching human or greater-than-human levels of intelligence, even in scholar realm (Luo et al., 2025), we should understand what kind of research practices keep humans in the loop, augment their comprehension, exploration, and collaboration ability, and empower their decision-making processes. Even as we "give up" on our intelligence superiority and claim firmly our creativity superiority, the latest progress in AI development and their evaluation against human creativity tests warns us that even that pedestal is not a safe harbour for us anymore (Koivisto and Grassini, 2023).

In the Digital Humanities (DH), creative processes have an additional importance, and research in the field must reflect this. While LLMs are proven to help and boost creative processes and therefore augment human creativity, the recent findings show that the AI models inhibit human creativity in the long run, leaving humans at a below-standard capacity when they are afterwards left on their own without LLM augmentation (Kumar et al., 2024). All that reminds us of the critical importance of the current moment in which scholars, together with the rest of humanity, find themselves. It is a moment where humanity becomes increasingly dependent on AI models and their help, and where evolutionarily we are about to deliver more and more agencies to AI and grow more reliant on the AI's decisions. A moment when we need to keep humans in the loop, and even more, to keep them on top of the creative and decision-making process.

Humanity, its knowledge, and even their working and creative processes, are digitized well enough to be able to "pull the break" now. On the other hand, it is proven that embracing new concepts is a more efficient survival strategy than fighting them (please see the example of "Sony" embracing digital music instead of fighting it (Liu, 2024), or "Kodak" fighting digital photography instead of embracing it (Gann, 2016)). Therefore, it is possible to argue that a wise but equally risky strategy is to embrace the AI models and their help, while keeping human on top of the loop. One of the core requirements is

to keep AI transparent and explainable (XAI) (Doshi-Velez and Kim, 2017), (Smuha et al., 2021), without the possibility to take over the decision-making process (but rather to inform it) (Wagner, 2019) and actions (but rather to perform them on demand) (Wagner, 2019). This is tantamount to keeping AI "in the box" (Tabesh, 2022) and avoiding *automation bias* (Kupfer et al., 2023). This is the core of the concept of "human-on-the-loop".

Reproducible research (Arnold et al., 2019), (Munafò et al., 2017) shares the same principles as keeping human-on-the-loop and transparent and explainable AI. In most scientific contexts, this approach to scientific research, publishing and grant application (Roelandse et al., 2023) is increasingly expected. Similarly, workflow-supported research shares multiple principles with reproducible research, primarily revolving around the need for a structured, transparent research process that ensures reliability and reproducibility of scientific findings together with sharing, verification and reuse of research outcomes (Demchenko et al., 2023), (Wratten et al., 2021). As such, workflows are one of the key enablers of reproducible research while also providing direct benefits to researchers who practice them. They also support the human-on-the-loop principle by providing a clear understanding of the process and enabling confidence in its management through structured support for transparent AI interventions.

Workflows are not a common practice in Digital Humanities (DH) research which contributes to the lower commitment to and number of reproducible research in DH work. However, the tide is changing in the DH arena with introduction of workflow-supported platforms and DH-workflow repositories (markets) like SSHOM (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace)¹ (Barbot et al., 2024). To our knowledge, none of the workflow-supported platforms, to date, are task-generic (like Gephi or OpenRefine). Nor are they DH-specific or DH-friendly (like Jupyter Notebooks², Galaxy³, and KNIME⁴).

In this paper, we present our contribution: the *Bukvik + ColaboFlow + LitTerra* ecosystem (fig. 1, where Colabo⁵, KnAllEdge⁶, and DataTalks⁷ are less relevant aspects of the ecosystem in the context of this work). *Bukvik*⁸ is a specialized distributed plat-

¹SSH Open Marketplace - Workflows: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?categories=workflow>

²Jupyter Notebook: <https://jupyter.org/>

³Galaxy Project - Workflows: <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/covid19/workflows/>

⁴KNIME Analytics Platform: <https://www.knime.com/knime-analytics-platform>

⁵<https://colabo.space/en/home/>

⁶<https://colabo.space/en/knowledge/>

⁷<https://colabo.space/en/datatalks/>

⁸<https://litterra.net/en/bukvik/>

form for running general workflows (even though currently primarily focused on stylometric multi-lingual analysis) and based on the implementation of the *ColaboFlow* workflow framework. *LitTerra*⁹ is a DH hybrid-reading platform, with all their underlying components augmented with AI assistants capable of AI insights, generation and interventions. Internally it integrates the *ColaboFlow* workflow framework¹⁰ and runs as SaaS (System as a Flow) where the majority of its business logic runs as *ColaboFlow* workflows. Both Bukvik and LitTerra platforms present examples of DH-friendly and generic workflow environments that promote reproducible research and supports the human-on-the-loop principle. Through this paper, we argue how the presented ecosystems supports DH research and creative processes and enable the transparency and explainability of the DH work and AI interventions.

This paper targets multiple audiences; (1) DH researchers and scholars that are not familiar with workflows but are interested to practice them and increase reproducible research in their work, (2) DH researchers and scholars who are familiar with workflows and want to embrace the tools that inherently support them (like Bukvik and LitTerra), (3) DH researchers and developers who experiment with DH platforms and tools and want to understand how to use workflows in their platforms, (4) workflow developers and researchers that want to practice workflows in real world scenarios, specifically in DH research, but also in the general context that *ColaboFlow* provides for, and finally (5) AI researchers and developers who want to understand how to augment workflow management and AI-augmentation in general with an ethical and critical approach to human+AI symbiotic research and keeping the human *on* the loop.

First, we present several aspects of reproducible research, its challenges and benefits, and how to increase the DH-researcher's motivation to adopt them (the section 2). Aligned to that analysis, we introduce relevant and key aspects of the Bukvik+*ColaboFlow*+*LitTerra* ecosystem that contribute to the reproducible research and "human-on-the-loop" principle (the section 4), explaining their contribution and demonstrating it wherever possible with existing implementation and screenshots or workflows. After that, we present, the "*solidification*" process (the section 5) as a methodology for transforming a (potentially) vague and declarative description of a research process into a solid, executable, and reproducible workflow through a set of transformative and evolutionary phases that aim to reduce the

frictions of digitizing the work process while fostering the creative aspects of such a transformation.

Finally, we conclude the paper (the section 7) and present potential future directions (the section 8). We present future work related to each of the solidification phases in the subsections related to each phase.

2 REPRODUCIBLE RESEARCH AND WHY IT MATTERS

The concepts of reproducible research (Munafò et al., 2017), (Goodman et al., 2016) are recognized and acknowledged as foundational principles of conducting scientific research for most of the scientific disciplines (Goodman et al., 2016), (Horton et al., 2022), especially with research involving data analysis and computational methods (Peng, 2011). However compared to "*hard sciences*" the Digital Humanities (DH) field is still struggling with the adoption of these principles (Joyeux-Prunel, 2024). The reasons for this include the complexity and interdisciplinarity involved in the research process, the lack of standardization in the field but also the unclear status of digital humanities, orbiting between scientific discipline and highly interdisciplinary field (Luhmann and Burghardt, 2022). All that, with the non-binary nature of the research objects and the natural tendency of the humanities to be more interpretative and subjective in nature (Medvedev, 2023) and the often collaboration with artists and other non-academic stakeholders, demotivates scholars to adopt the reproducibility principles. Additionally, DH research often requires a creative process which is hard to document and reproduce due to its tacit nature and need to "*be in a flow*" (Czikszentmihalyi, 1990) and uninterrupted by formalization and standardization.

On the other hand, most of the frameworks, standards and tools for enabling reproducible research are often complex, difficult for scholars that became computer literate by need and finally, the whole investment in such tools is with a low ROI ("*return of investment*") for DH scholars. This is significantly different in "hard science" and traditionally computational-heavy disciplines (like physics, bioinformatics, earth science, astronomy, chemistry) where the investment in reproducibility tools is justified by the high ROI through the very nature of the research process and during the research process itself providing a clear incentive and benefits for the researchers to adopt the reproducibility principles or rather the "*Five*

⁹<https://litterra.net/en/litterra/>

¹⁰<https://colabo.space/en/flow/>

Figure 1: ColaboFlow Ecosystem: Bukvik + ColaboFlow + LitTerra

selfish reasons to work reproducibly” (Markowetz, 2015). Interestingly, just in USA “... *irreproducible preclinical research exceeds 50%, resulting in approximately US\$28,000,000,000 (US\$28B)/year spent on preclinical research that is not reproducible*” (Freedman et al., 2015).

However, benefits of reproducibility and documenting DH research work, process and experiments is non-negligible. It helps in transparency of the process, its dissemination and reuse, and in the validation of the results. It clearly enables more efficient collaboration and education and in preservation of digitally-born artifacts and all the “*selfish*” reasons mentioned (Markowetz, 2015) still apply in DH. Unfortunately, the path to reproducibility usually stops at Open Data, at the next step FAIRness (*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable*) and Open Science principles. The FAIR principles are not enough to ensure reproducibility of the research process and its results, but they are a good starting point. The next step is to ensure that the research process is documented in a way that it can be reproduced by others. This is where workflows come into play.

Even with the benefits of reproducibility being moderately clear, there is no agenda neither between scholars nor the tools, infrastructures or platform

providers on supporting such kind of research and making it ubiquitous (and *enabled-by-design*) in the field. It is important to mention the SSH OM initiative¹¹ that aims to bring an unified platform for declarative and semantically describing workflows, the tools being used in the workflow steps and the datasets used or produced (Concordia et al., 2020).

Here we assemble a list of principles and features (a *DH agenda*) which we have identified as the ones which integration in research infrastructures should help in and motivate the adoption of reproducibility in DH:

Reproducibility Principles:

- i. **low-cost** adaption - adaption reproducible aspects of research should be low-cost tasks where the underlying tools and infrastructure would enable it ideally without an additional effort on the researchers’ side. Recent economic analyses estimate that achieving high reproducibility can be accomplished at a relatively low per-paper cost (Colliard et al., 2021).
- ii. **promptly benefits** - the benefits of investing in reproducible research should be promptly available, so instead of thinking of long term benefits we should provide more or less immediate benefits,

¹¹SSH Open Market: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

which would be harder to achieve with a conventional approach. Reproducible research provides immediate organizational and personal benefits, such as easier project continuation and knowledge transfer (or benefitting to *'our future self'* (Rasmussen et al., 2023)).

- iii. **increase research comprehension and tacit knowledge** - using the research platforms should increase the understanding of research design and its implementation. They should also increase the level of tacit knowledge captured as a *"side-effect"*. Integrating models that address both explicit and tacit knowledge can improve the transfer and comprehension of research processes (Niedderer and Imani, 2009).
- iv. **collaboration** - In the context of reproducible research, collaboration is not only about sharing the final results but also about the research process. The research platform should be designed to support real time collaboration on designing and implementing the research process and data as an incentive to the researcher.
- v. **provenance** - research data provenance is central requirement for reproducibility (Sahoo et al., 2019). It enables the researcher to track the history of the data and their evolution. It helps researchers to work more efficiently and confidently through the research process, modify it and comprehend data evolution and the final results.
- vi. **versioning** - similarly to provenance, support for versioning of datasets and research process gives researchers additional confidence and motivates them to modify the research process for the sake of additional experimentation, validation of other experiment variants, among others. The absence of systematic versioning is a major barrier to reproducibility (a *"reproducibility crisis"*, (Klump et al.,))
- vii. **visibility** - research platform should visualize research work (as a blueprint of the research process), its progress, and its final and selected intermediate results. Transparent and visible research processes are foundational to reproducibility and scientific rigor (Nosek et al., 2025).
- viii. **help readers** - conducting research through a research platform should provide additional outcomes that should help readers and reviewers with their comprehension and confidence in the research process and its results.
- ix. **increase innovation and creativity** - research platform should promote creativity of the research process through various aspects; (1) the method-

ologies incorporated should have creative aspects, (2) it should incorporate frameworks (templates) and constraints which are known to foster creativity, (3) sharing and collaboration on research process enables creative brainstorming, creative-leaps and even crowd-sourced innovation and creativity.

- x. **keep the Flow** - for the creative (research) processes common to the field of Digital Humanities where scholars are often participate in PAR (Participatory action research) with actors or other participants that are *in a flow*, the platform should help keeping the flow and provide a low friction.
- xi. **immerse in hybrid interaction** - in the post-pandemic work often both researchers' work and their PAR engagement is placed in a hybrid space and therefore the research platform should enable immersion in both real and virtual worlds and provide seamless transition between them.

3 WORKFLOWS, REPRODUCIBILITY AND COLABOFLOW

This section briefly introduces workflows and presents the ways in which they are implemented within the ColaboFlow framework. It then argues how practicing workflow methodology supports reproducible research. Finally, it elaborates on ColaboFlow's design and implementation, which embrace reproducibility in the framework or any platform developed on top of it.

3.1 Workflows

We conceive of a workflow as a sequence of tasks or actions that model some physical or conceptual process. Within the scope of this paper, we focus primarily on conceptual processes and, more precisely, on research processes. As such, workflows are always approximations or models of the real processes. As such, they are never perfect representations, nor do we aim to achieve that, but rather to carefully balance between the two trends of required accuracy and desired simplicity. This is one of the main reasons why workflows and processes in general are modeled with various modeling languages (Pankowska, 2019), (Bork et al., 2020), (Bork et al., 2018).

In ColaboFramework, we chose BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation) (Recker, 2008) as a workflow modeling language. At (fig. 2), a reader can find a simple BPMN workflow example presented in

the ColaboFlow Framework. It is a workflow for importing TEI-XML documents into the LitTerra platform, which has a start event followed by three sequential tasks connected with sequence flows, and finalized with an end event. The tasks are annotated with their names.

Our motivation for choosing BPMN for workflow representation in ColaboFlow is multifold; (i) BPMN is a well-established standard for modeling business processes, (ii) it is widely used and supported by many tools, both for visualization and execution, (iii) it is very expressive and flexible, allowing us to model complex processes with conditional branching and parallel execution, (iv) it is designed to be easily understandable by both technical and non-technical users, which inherently reduces the socio-technical gap and frictions in the process of modeling and executing workflows, (v) it has rich mechanisms for extending the language with custom elements and attributes, which we use to extend the processes into hybrid and socio-technical processes (Rudan et al., 2021).

Workflows as a design paradigm have multiple benefits for researchers and their research processes, which include transparency, reproducibility, fostering creativity, collaboration, and bridging the socio-technical gap between researchers, developers, tools, and research outcomes.

Having a formal standard for describing and decomposing the research process into tasks and their relationships enables researchers to visualize their research process, to document it in a structured and standardized manner, and to share it with others more easily. It also externalises and fosters the design process and critical thinking over the research process, which is often tacit and not documented. This is especially important in DH research, where the research process is often complex and interdisciplinary, and involves multiple stakeholders and perspectives. All that we further embrace and expand in the concrete ColaboFlow framework implementation.

Once we go beyond a basic *“taxative”* workflow methodology and use more advanced workflow entities, such as gateways (forks, unions, sequential or parallel execution), events (start, end, intermediate), and data objects (input, output, and data stores), we can model more complex processes and their relationships. *Gateways* embed and communicate conditioning and various research paths in the research flow and the reasoning behind them. *Data objects* provide additional context and information about the data, their type, and potentially their provenance. These new entities are sufficiently powerful to model much more complex and complete (real-world) re-

search processes. Yet, they are still easy to understand and use, which is one of the key benefits of the workflow methodology.

We can see an example of such a workflow in the (fig. 3) where we have an example of a stylometric workflow that uses POS (Part Of Speech) tagger and analyzes an L2 (second-language) corpus to explore the cases in the text that have two adjectives in front of nouns. As one can see, we utilize two types of gateways: (i) an *exclusive* gateway for choosing between the corpus language and (ii) an *inclusive* gateway for merging the control flow of the two possible paths (tasks). We have also used *data objects* to represent the input and output data of the tasks (corpus metadata, corpus data, and annotated corpus metadata). We have also used *task type annotations* (BPMN *decorators*) to annotate the tasks with their type, e.g. *service task* for most tasks and *user or manual task* for the last task, which is a manual task that involves human intervention (exploring the generated POS annotations).

We will address the other benefits of using the workflow methodology now in the following paragraphs, with the special emphasis on the *“reproducibility principles”* (enumerated in the list 2 of the sec. 2). Please note that the principles that are not covered with workflows but rather with the ColaboFlow framework extension will be covered separately in the (subsection 3.2) instead.

Reproducibility Principles achieved through practicing workflow methodology

- i. **low-cost** adoption - workflows are straightforward in nature and conceptually *“cheap”* to adopt as modeling constructs. The cost of adoption is directly related to the quality and the simplicity of the tool that provides the workflow support (an aspect we address in the ColaboFlow (subsection below 3.2).
- ii. **promptly benefits** - the promptly benefits are several: (i) the researcher or research group have a protocol for documenting their work as they (ii) share it with others, (iii) can investigate their research process more easily and (iv) handle alternative hypothesis or settings (*“forking”*) in a safer way.
- iii. increase **research comprehension** and **tacit knowledge** - As explained above, visualizing the research flow increases research comprehension and opens possibilities for referring to specific tasks, elaborating on them, and capturing tacit knowledge through that process.
- iv. **collaboration** - The workflow methodology itself is not a key enabler of collaboration (please re-

Figure 2: BPMN Workflow Example in ColaboFlow Framework

Figure 3: ColaboFlow Presentation: An advanced BPMN Workflow Example in ColaboFlow Framework - Two adjectives in front of nouns

fer to the ColaboFlow (subsection 3.2)). However, as a structured approach to documenting and sharing research processes, it provides shareable artefacts and fosters a collaborative environment where researchers can easily engage with each other's work.

- v. **provenance** - workflows shared alongside research outcomes provide an additional level of reliability by recording the provenance of research results.
- vi. **versioning** - externalizing the research process into workflow diagrams will enable versioning if a scholar versions workflow diagrams or uses a store that supports versioning.
- vii. **visibility** - workflows visualize research, though there remains a need for more advanced mechanisms to visualize its progress and results.
- viii. **help readers** - they help readers and reviewers with their comprehension and ensure confidence in the research process and its results.
- ix. **increase innovation and creativity** - workflow as a methodology innovation. For instance, the Data Workflow Method (DWM) has been shown

to break organizational silos and create multi-disciplinary teams, thereby fostering innovation at the systemic level (Li et al., 2023).

It is worth mentioning that workflows can have various interpretations and implementations, where each of them has its benefits and its application field.

First of all, there are classic or *control flow* workflows that describe the flow (order) of work. In these, each task represents a specific action or activity that needs to be performed. In such workflows, our main focus is on the order of tasks, decisions, and branching logic. This is the most common interpretation of a workflow, and it is the one used in the BPMN standard, and as such, it is the one inferred in the ColaboFlow framework.

However, there are also *data workflows* that focus on the flow of data and its transformation through the process. In this case, the tasks focus more on data manipulation and transformation than on the control flow. Tasks are also triggered with data-readiness rather than with the control flow, and with the previous task being executed and finished.

Finally, there are also hybrid workflows that combine both control and data flows. In this case, tasks

can address both control flow and data manipulation. This is the case with the ColaboFlow framework, where we focus on dataset management and dataset evolution through the workflow execution (subsection 3.2.3), and therefore on providing support for both control- and data-flows (which is an extension to common and standard BPMN execution.)

3.2 ColaboFlow

ColaboFlow (a part of Colabo.Space ecosystem¹²) is a workflow methodology / framework designed to describe generic systems through visually represented (work)flows or processes¹³. Its visual representation is based on partially-specialized BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation) standard¹⁴ which offers a set of graphical elements used to create a visual representation of a workflow (Rudan et al., 2021). This is a valuable asset for DH research as it enables the researchers to visually represent their research process and to document it in a structured and standardized manner. It contains, further, additional support for hybrid (real-world and online) processes, social processes and DH-specific research processes (like partial support for data-flows, among others). The visual component responsible for the BPMN visualization and editing is an extension of the open source and modular Camunda solution for BPMN¹⁵ while the execution engine is implemented in the ColaboFlow framework itself and it is based

From the perspective of implementation, ColaboFlow is implemented following the ideas of *petri nets* (Reisig, 2012) and their core concept, *tokens*. More precisely, it is implemented in an extension version of petri nets, called *coloured petri nets* (Jensen, 1987) where tokens have their own "*personality*", are distinguishable among each other and can carry additional information; this becomes a critical feature in the context of provenance (section 3.2.4), dataflows and dataset management.

In the following subsections, we address the key aspects of the ColaboFlow framework, especially those that are novel extensions to the general implementation of workflows and those that are critical for DH research and the reproducibility principles. Before that, however, we quickly summarize them in parallel to the reproducible principles list (list 3.1).

Reproducibility Principles achieved through

¹²Colabo.Space ecosystem - <https://colabo.space/>

¹³ColaboFlow framework: <https://colabo.space/en/flow/>

¹⁴BPMN - Business Process Model and Notation: <https://www.omg.org/bpmn/>

¹⁵BPMN Camunda: <https://bpmn.io/>

¹⁶BPMN Camunda: <https://bpmn.io/>

¹⁷ColaboWare - <https://cha-os.org/en/colaboware/>

specific features of ColaboFlow framework

- i. **low-cost** adaptation - ColaboFlow integrates easy-to-use open source and modular Camunda solution for BPMN visualizing and editing¹⁶.
- ii. **promptly benefits** - it provides immediate value to researchers; they can draw workflows, improve, and execute them (eventually), among other things.
- iii. increase **research comprehension** and **tacit knowledge** - through the ColaboFlow framework, researchers can connect flows with datasets and data sources, metadata, and additional external knowledge. They can, further, describe tasks and connect them to the tools through which they are implemented.
- iv. **collaboration** - ColaboFlow has deeply integrated collaboration support, enabling collaboration at every stage of the research process.
- v. **provenance** - ColaboFlow inherently enables provenance of data, associating them with the workflow that produces that data.
- vi. **versioning** - Similarly to provenance, ColaboFlow allows versioning and multi-truth support for each aspect of the workflow.
- vii. **visibility** - ColaboFlow artefacts are sharable and possible to relate to any artefact of the research process.
- viii. **help readers** - if the ColaboFlow framework is fully enabled, it allows for full traceability of the research process and its execution, even allowing easy reproduction and close+distant reading support.
- ix. **increase innovation and creativity** - ColaboFlow as an open platform allows integration of various methodologies. One of them is the *solidification* methodology itself that provides creativity and creative constraints, collaboration, brainstorming and crowd-sourced innovation.
- x. **keep the Flow** - ColaboFlow supports low friction integration with participants and integration with physical and digital tools (ColaboWare¹⁷) that can be used in the research process.
- xi. immerse in **hybrid interaction** - ColaboFlow framework was successfully integrated in mobile

(PWA) applications and evaluated highly positively in usability tests.

3.2.1 Key ColaboFlow Design Principles

Before addressing the key aspects of the ColaboFlow framework and its novel approaches to workflows and reproducibility support, we present the key design principles that guided the ColaboFlow framework design and implementation as they are more universal and draw the other design decisions.

1. **Standards** - ColaboFlow framework is based on standards.
2. **Federated Knowledge** - ColaboFlow framework supports federated knowledge, allowing researchers to connect their workflows with external data sources and knowledge bases.
3. **Interoperability** - ColaboFlow framework is interoperable with other tools and platforms.
4. **Usability** - ColaboFlow framework is designed to be easy to use and to have a low learning curve.
5. **Framework** - ColaboFlow is a framework designed to support continuous and ubiquitous work environments rather than discrete tasks.
6. **Collaboration** - ColaboFlow framework is designed to support collaboration and to enable researchers to work together on the same workflow.
7. **Open Source** - ColaboFlow framework is open source and modular.

For example the first design principle, *standards*, is reflected in the choice of BPMN as a workflow modeling language, which is a widely accepted standard for modeling business processes. The second design principle, *federated knowledge*, is reflected in the ability to connect workflows with general artefacts (through the KnAllEdge store) and external data sources and knowledge bases. The third design principle, *interoperability*, is reflected in the ability to integrate ColaboFlow with other tools and platforms, such as Bukvik and LitTerra. The fourth design principle, *usability*, is reflected in the choice of Camunda as a BPMN visualization and editing tool, which is easy to use and has a low learning curve (please see the (fig. 3) for an example of simplicity of presentation and (fig. 4) for an example of simplicity of editing workflows). The fifth design principle, *framework*, is reflected in the fact that ColaboFlow is designed to support continuous and ubiquitous work environments rather than discrete tasks. The sixth design principle, *collaboration*, is reflected in the ability to collaborate on workflows and to share them with others. Finally, the seventh design principle, *open*

source, is reflected in the fact that ColaboFlow is open source and modular.

3.2.2 Tokens

Most workflow implementations that support workflow execution, such as BPMN, are based on the *control flow* paradigm where the execution is controlled by execution *tokens*. These are passed through the workflow tasks and the sequences connecting them. Tokens "*originate*" from Petri nets (Reisig, 2012) and due to their general importance in the workflow execution, but also our novel approach to the tokens usage, we will pay special attention to them together with the follow-up diagrams.

Figure 5: Petri net example

First, (fig. 5) shows a simple Petri net example with 4 places (red circles), two transitions (blue squares) and arcs between the places and transitions (green arrows), and finally two tokens (yellow circles) placed in places. Tokens are places of "*execution*" saying that execution happens in P_{S1} and P_{S2} places. The execution state changes with tokens changing places. For example, if transition T_1 fires, the token would move from P_{S1} to P_{E1} . This would fulfill the requirements for transition T_2 (all the input places have tokens in them) and let it fire and move the tokens from P_{E1} and P_{S2} to P_{E2} . /

Figure 6: Petri net workflow equivalent of the BPMN workflow from the (fig. 2)

With the Petri net "*apparatus*" established, we

Figure 4: ColaboFlow Editing: An advanced BPMN Workflow Example in ColaboFlow Framework

can now make an equivalent Petri net workflow for the basic workflow presented by (fig. 2). The Petri net equivalent of the BPMN workflow is presented by (fig. 6). As one can see, the Petri net equivalent of the BPMN workflow has 4 places, 3 transitions and 3 tokens, where the first and the last place represent the start and end event, respectively, in the BPMN workflow. The transitions are equivalent to the BPMN tasks, and the arcs are equivalent to the BPMN sequence flows. The tokens are placed in the start place, and move through the workflow as the tasks are executed. The Petri net equivalent of the BPMN workflow is a powerful representation of the workflow execution, as it allows us to visualize execution progress.

However, when it comes to implementing workflows for the sake of execution, as in the case of ColaboFlow, we would quickly notice the significant issue with the Petri net representation of workflow execution. Namely, the tasks-equivalents in Petri nets do not encompass time. The fact that a particular task is *being* executed, as in Petri nets, the tokens are "running" through the tasks and do not "wait" for the task to be executed, as is the case in real-world workflows and long-running tasks. This motivates us to present a more sophisticated model of the tasks in the Petri net representation, which incorporates the notion of time and task states. Accordingly, (a) and (b) in (fig. 7) show the before- and after-execution states of the simplified task, (c) presents the "synchronous" task model that can be in the "running" state, and (d) presents the "asynchronous" task model that can "wait" for the execution to finish.

Finally, we can now present the Petri net equivalent of the BPMN workflow with the task states incorporated in the (fig. 8), where each sub-diagram ("a" to "d") consists of a BPMN workflow (upper part of sub-diagram) and its Petri net equivalent (lower part of the sub-diagram). For the task T_1 , we used asynchronous task implementation (fig. 7 (d)) and for the task T_2 , we used synchronous task implementation (fig. 7 (c)). We can see in the (c) sub-diagram that the task T_1 is being finished by the execution system adding a token to the P_{T1F} place. This is a way to say that the work that the task represents is done and that task can proceed to the finish state and we can start executing the next task (T_2).

The benefits of providing workflow execution through a token concept are powerful in that it provides a clear and transparent view of workflow execution and insights into its current execution status and all the relevant contextual entities. Therefore, tokens enable real-time monitoring and debugging of the workflow execution. Since tokens can hold the "context" of the execution, they also enable workflow execution to be distributed, scalable and managed (paused, resumed, or with long-running tasks) in a distributed environment. To support the context, we must introduce the extension of Petri nets called *coloured petri nets* (Jensen, 1987). The main difference is that tokens in the coloured petri nets are not indistinguishable. Rather, they can carry additional information, which is called the "colour" of the token, and that colour can be used to represent execution context. Readers can find the definition of the token adopted in the ColaboFlow framework in the

Figure 7: Variants (modeling time) of Petri Net model of BPMN Task

Figure 8: Example of the execution states of a workflow with two tasks

code snippet (code 1). As we can see, there is the id of the running workflow ('flowInstanceId'), the id of the place where the token is currently present ('placeId'), and the id of the place instance (in regard to the running workflow instance) where the token is currently present ('placeInstanceId'), among other attributes. We will address the 'dataEntryReferences' attribute in the subsection (sec. 3.2.3).

Listing 1: ColaboFlow Token interface (an excerpt)

```

1 /**
2  * Coloured token (Petri-net concept of
3  * executional presence)
4  */
5  export interface IFlowToken {
6  /** an id of the token */
7  id: string;
8
9  /** the id of the flow instance this token
10 belongs to */
11 flowInstanceId: string;
12
13 /** at what place (task, activity, event,
14 gateway, ...) the token is currently
15 present */
16 placeId: string;
17
18 /** at what place instance (task, activity,
19 gateway, ...) the token is currently
20 present */
21 placeInstanceId: string;

```

```

    event, gateway, ...) the token is
    currently present */
15 placeInstanceId: string;
16
17 /** the id of the creator of the token */
18 whoAmI: string;
19
20 /** the type of the agent that created the
    token */
21 agentType: RIMA_AGENT_TYPE;
22
23 /**
24  * the list of the task outputs (results)
    acquired during the token lifetime (
    workflow traversing)
25  */
26 dataEntryReferences:
    IDataTalksCacheEntryReference[];
27 }

```

They also allow an easy mechanism of human-in-the-loop interventions where (i) we create an execution token to start the workflow on behalf of the workflow-initiator (and use ‘whoAmI’ and ‘agentType’ attributes to designate it) and (ii) we “*delegate*” the execution token to the task-performer to run a task manually (for example the last task in fig. 3), and provide them with a special type of task that has a visual interface intended to support human interaction with datasets.

3.2.3 Dataflows and Datasets

As we have already mentioned, there are various interpretations of workflows, and while the more standard one (the one that BPMN is based on) is the *control flow* workflow, there are also *data workflows* that focus on the flow of data and its transformation through the process. In this case, the tasks focus more on data manipulation and transformation than the control flow. Tasks are also triggered with data-readiness rather with the control flow and by the previous task having been executed and finished.

Considering that DH research is often data-intensive and that datasets are the core of the research process, there is a strong interest in data workflows and methodologies that would support data transformation and evolution through the research process. Therefore, ColaboFlow framework introduces a novel approach of utilizing coloured tokens to support *hybrid workflows* - a fusion of control and data flows in the workflows.

In other words, while tokens are originally used to represent the execution flow of the workflow, in the ColaboFlow framework they are also used to represent the datasets that are being processed and transformed through the workflow by transformation tasks.

A research workflow designer can decide if they want to use that extended approach or not, and if yes, for which sections (paths) of the overall workflow. In this way, researchers can combine the control flow and data flow in the same workflow, keeping the benefits of both approaches.

To achieve that, we utilize the ‘dataEntryReferences’ attribute of the token (code 1), which is a list of references to the datasets that are being processed by the tasks that the token is passing through. Each reference is an instance of the ‘IDataTalksCacheEntryReference’ interface that contains the reference to the dataset, its type, and other relevant information. The datasets can be of various types, e.g. textual documents, images, audio files, etc.

Here, we want to point out an effective methodology that ColaboFlow can provide: the “*evolution of a dataset*” throughout the workflow execution. Consider (fig. 9) where we have a simple workflow that processes a text and extracts its stylometric features. At the workflow we can see the set of selected (coloured) tasks. Those tasks constitute the dataset’s evolution path that leads from the original un-preprocessed text to a visually annotated HTML of the relevant experts; the final state of the dataset evolution.

Thanks to the execution token’s captured trace, a user investigating the “*generate HTML excerpts*” task, can explore the dataset’s evolutionary path, or rather its provenance (sec. 3.2.4). This is possible as the execution token in that task carries (refers to) all the datasets produced by tasks across the token’s evolutionary path across the workflow execution. This powerful approach allows us to visualize the datasets’ evolution and to track their provenance through the workflow execution.

3.2.4 Provenance

Following the previous subsection, we can argue that the ColaboFlow framework inherently enables the provenance of datasets by associating them with the workflows producing them, but even deeper, the tasks generating them, and deeper still, the evolutionary paths tracing the dataset of interest backward to the original dataset.

This original approach provides, in utilizing workflow tokens, a shift in conceptualizing and implementing research work from the BPMN original approach – primarily a control-flow (*task-oriented*) design paradigm - to a data-flow (*data-oriented paradigm*). The **task-oriented paradigm** *thinks* in terms of the tasks that are executed in a sequence (or a more complex flow) where each task has its input data, input parameters and output data. The task-oriented paradigm

Figure 9: ColaboFlow - Dataflow Workflow Example

does not inherently engage with the origin, nor does it *pass-through* that origin, or keep the provenance and track the modification of data. In such a manner, the system generates, instead of a single-evolving dataset, new and new semantically unrelated datasets on each task. The **data-oriented paradigm** promoted by the ColaboFlow dataflow paradigm and enabled by the token implementation of their execution in the ColaboFlow platform, frames research thinking around a set of tasks that are responsible for providing transformation or *evolution* of datasets toward the ideal or satisfying datasets (fig. 9). In a nutshell, they remember their origin and, what is more important, their evolutionary process and they semantically represent the same datasets. In that sense, the datasets that are outputs (or rather outcomes) of each specific task, instead of being conceived as new datasets, should be rather recognized as *snapshots* of the datasets evolution across the workflow. This would additionally help in debugging the data-flow or observing intermediate research results.

3.2.5 Collaboration

ColaboFlow has deeply integrated collaboration support, enabling collaboration on workflows, tasks, datasets, gateways (allowing collaborators to argue any decision logic) and naturally on the final results. A researcher can discuss the research processes (in the context of obtaining the findings), or hypotheses provided in the real-world (externally) or as part of the platform.

Each artefact of the research process, which can be a workflow, task, dataset, or research observation, is stored in the platform's store, KnAllEdge¹⁸. This is a graph-like store that allows researchers to connect their artefacts with each other and to create a network of related artefacts. Similarly, a basic set of activities can be performed on any KnAllEdge artefact, like commenting, discussing, tagging, and sharing. This allows researchers to collaborate on their research processes and to share their findings with others.

This makes natural the scenario where one researcher questions a specific tool used for the task ex-

ecution, while the other answers in a followup chat and references, in the same chat, other KnAllEdge artefacts, like datasets that support the discussion and argumentation.

3.2.6 SaaS - System as a Flow

What is interesting about the implementation of LitTerra's hybrid-reading platform is that it is *itself* workflow-driven. Apart from the obvious benefits of an *eating-your-own-dog-food* approach, most of the features and activities inside LitTerra are transparent and comprehensible to users due to its nature as a workflows-embedded DH-platform. This means that we have *transparency* and *confidence* on how LitTerra's internal features are implemented, and a reader can see an example of an excerpt of workflows enabled in LitTerra platform (fig. 10).

We can also use them as puzzles or building blocks and recreate a new kind of LitTerra feature from an existing one. This enables the platform to be flexible and to adapt to new research requirements and practices. Take, for example, the "Search Corpus Against a Query" flow where the first task, "Expand search query," is an extension of a regular search flow. This task enables fuzzy search in LitTerra, adding support for searching across synonyms and, even further, across all the corpus languages and their synonyms. This is thanks to the partnering platform "EZGlot"¹⁹, a fundamentally critical feature when it comes to close reading of multilingual corpora.

ColaboFlow is designed to support various execution environments, from the *local* frontend execution (as with LitTerra platform) to *backend* and *distributed* execution (as with the Bukvik platform) or *cloud* execution. It is also possible to have *hybrid* execution where some tasks are executed locally and some are executed in the backend, or even a *fluid* execution where tasks are executed in the environment deemed most suitable or preset by the workflow designer. This is a powerful feature as it allows researchers to execute their workflows in the environment that best fits their research process and adapt to their research's changing requirements. Additionally, this approach addresses the continuously grow-

¹⁸KnAllEdge - <https://colabo.space/en/knalledge/>

¹⁹EZGlot platform: <https://www.ezglot.com/about>

ing concern about *privacy and data protection* as researchers can execute their workflows in a local environment without the need to share their data with external services or platforms.

3.2.7 Solidification

ColaboFlow is designed to support the "solidification" process and, as such, allows various levels of flow complexity, from barely conceived and described with a high level of abstraction to a fully detailed and executable flow. This allows various levels of the workflow methodology adoption, making it cheap to implement. On the one hand, researchers can use it just to describe their research process semantically, and on the another hand, they can execute their research processes as workflows. AI-supported solidification helps evolve the descriptive research process into a more structured and formalized one that can be eventually executed as a workflow. More on this in a separate section (sec. 5).

4 COLABOFLOW, BUKVIK, AND LITERRA AS A "HUMAN-ON-THE-LOOP" AI-AUGMENTED WORKFLOW PLATFORM

In this section, we present the Bukvik, ColaboFlow, and LitTerra ecosystem as a platform that supports reproducible research and the "human-on-the-loop" principle. We focus on the key features of the platform that contribute to both of them.

4.1 LitTerra

First, we will introduce the LitTerra platform. Figure (fig. 11) represents the LitTerra interface with the key components open and with two parallel texts, English and Serbian, viewed side-by-side.

The interface can be adapted for individual or collaborative research, bilingual reading and writing. In the following lists, we can identify the most important components that are relevant for the hybrid reading enumerated equally to the (fig. 11):

1. Two bilingual parallel texts aligned and presented in parallel views available for close reading
2. Integrated interactive visualization of stylometric (distant reading) results. This is a visualization of a dataset, which is an outcome of a Bukvik workflow executed in the ColaboFlow framework.

3. NUI (Natural user interface) - called "ColaboNUI" - AI-powered natural text (or speech) interaction with the UI (User Interface)
4. User and automatic annotations ("AnnoTatas") with the possibility of comments and collaboration on them. They can annotate the text, the workflow, the datasets, the tasks, and images, among others. There is support for multi-annotations.
5. Semantic editor (can be used for creative writing and editing texts) together with inline annotating the editing text in the WYSIWYG manner
6. Cross-annotation (multi-AnnoTata) refers to passages in both texts (or other media) at the same time, for example, to compare them.
7. Collaborative interface for real-time collaboration between users over any artifact that exists in LitTerra ecosystem

Most of the interaction with LitTerra is possible through free natural user interaction (NUI) using either free natural text commands or even speech control.

4.2 Bukvik

Bukvik is a specialized set of workflows in the ColaboFlow framework that is integrated in the LitTerra platform. It supports common research workflows that address distant reading, stylometry and parallel multilingual corpora. The Bukvik workflows are designed to be task-generic, DH-specific, and DH-friendly. Bukvik used to exist as an independent platform with a form of hybrid (data+control)-driven flows. Eventually, it has been migrated as an instance (implementation) of the ColaboFlow framework and, as such, became more aligned with generic workflow principles, standardized and gained benefits from a broader corpus of workflow R&D.

At the (fig. 12), one can see the Bukvik workflow for the stylometric and network analysis of multilingual texts (presented through the example of Nabokov's "Lolita"). As such, the workflow has been a source of extensive multilingual stylometry research. The workflow is designed to support *reproducibility* in multiple ways. First, it can support various texts to run through the same workflow in parallel but independently, whereby each workflow instance produces an independent set of datasets associated with each specific text. Secondly, it supports the possibility of the same workflow being instantiated and working with different languages thanks to separate configuration parameters for each workflow instance. Such configuration parameters would choose

Figure 10: LitTerra - Internal-flows

the language-specific corpus, datasets and tools (tasks implementations), for example, a specific tagger for each language.

In a nutshell, the Bukvik platform is primarily a *ColaboFlow instance* empowered with a rich set of DH-specific tools, workflows and datasets. There is also a set of *workflow templates* (or *research scenarios*) together with similar types of recipes and instructions that tune both the framework and its AI augmentation according to the needs of Bukvik communities.

5 SOLIDIFICATION PRINCIPLES AND BENEFITS IN COLABOFLOW

Here, we present the *solidification process* and the set of contributing phases together with their benefits to the user and their workflow design process. The aim of the *solidification* process is to guide users and help them to transform a (potentially) vague and declarative description of a research project into a solid and semantically sound workflow, which have a capacity to evolve to a completely executable and reproducible workflow. This process happens incrementally, through a series of transformative and evolutionary solidification *phases*. Even though each phase has a specific role, their overall aim is (i) to help and provide guidance in *digitizing* the research process, (ii) to reduce frictions and ambiguities, and (iii)

to foster creativity and collaboration during digitization and (iv) to increase the captured tacit knowledge and quality and amount of its outcome.

With all being said, the solidification process that we propose rather than seen as *carved in stone* should be seen as a *fluid* process that is founded on the core principles and still being adaptable to the specific needs and context of the research project. In such way it still (i) promotes the core principles while it (ii) benefits on the personalization of the process to the specific needs of the research project and the researcher or it is (iii) open to specific additional sub-methodologies (like brainstorming or creative and design thinking methodologies.)

The core principles driving our design and that should be "questioned" against any modification of the solidification process are:

Solidification Principles:

- i. **Workflow-oriented** - naturally, solidification process promotes workflow design paradigm and implementation,
- ii. **Workflow-driven** - interestingly while it is promoting and driving workflow, the solidification process is implemented as a high-level or rather meta-workflow and as such it is workflow-driven (each phase is a meta-task of the meta-flow), declarative, transparent and modular, meaning that it promotes its own evolution and adaptability to specific needs and "personalizations",
- iii. **Incremental** - incremental and iterative, allowing

English 1897 (Charlotte Brontë)

Usage of exotic words (Serbian)

usage	Verbs (sr)	Nouns (sr)
1	~10	~10
2	~15	~15
3	~20	~20
4	~25	~25
5	~30	~30

Log (usage frequency in standard corpus)

1 **A** **N** О дупрала сам се целим путем. Било је то нешто ново с

2

3 **command** domain status started duration actions

Show 3 columns, 2 rows, and 1 frozen

command domain status started duration actions

Show Serbian translations Documents success 2 minutes ago 00:00:09

Running NLI Commands (1)

Previous NLI Commands (1)

4 **B** Госпођа? Како је он мој госпођар? Да ли сам ја његова служавка?

— Не, ви сте још своје издржавање. Мишљате о својој непослушности.

5 **B** Госпођа? Како је он мој госпођар? Да ли сам ја његова служавка?

— Не, ви сте још своје издржавање. Мишљате о својој непослушности.

6 **B** Госпођа? Како је он мој госпођар? Да ли сам ја његова служавка?

— Не, ви сте још своје издржавање. Мишљате о својој непослушности.

7

Грдећи ме тако, донеле су ме у собу, коју је госпођа Рид одређила, и бациле ме на столицу. Моја прва мисао била је да се нагло одупрем, али њихове руке намах су ме зграбиле.

— Ако не седите мирно, везаћемо вас — рече Беси. — Госпођице Абот, позајмите ми ваше подвезице, јер ће моје одмах пући.

Госпођица Абот се окренула да са своје дебеле ноге скине тражењу везу. Ове припреме за везивање и остале претње нису ме нарочитис узбуђивале.

— Не скидајте их — узвикнух — нећу се помаћи.

Да њих потврдила т 29

Гдега сам столицу држама.

— Гавите шта радите — рече Беси, и када се уверила да попуштам, престала је да ме стеже. Она и госпођица Абот су тада ставиле прекрштених руку, посматрајући ме сумњиво, као да су га побијали на нисам пла чистри светли

Comments

0 comments

Write a comment...

Figure 11: LitTerra - interface for hybrid (close + distant) reading and research

researchers to gradually refine their workflows,

Figure 12: Bukvik workflow - Stylometric Analysis cross-lingual analysis of Nabokov's Lolita

- iv. **Generous** - generous in skipping its phases and stopping before reaching the last phase and still being beneficial and comprehensible to users,
 - v. **Dialogue as transformation** - the solidification process is dialogic, allowing researchers to interact with other researchers and agents, where dialogue itself transforms both the research workflow and research knowledge,
 - vi. **Augmented** - allowing researchers to leverage automation/ML/AI capabilities to enhance and simplify their process,
 - vii. **Human-on-the-loop** - ensures the maximum transparency and explainability of the designing (resulting) workflow, and promotes and places human decisions "placeholders" in it,
 - viii. **Evaluative** - it evaluates the progress, quality and status of the solidification of a workflow, and provides feedback,
 - ix. **Critical** - it is critical to users production of workflows, comparing the current state with the expected and commonly achieved workflow qualities, and therefore:
 - x. **Gate-keeping** - it protects, or rather suggests, when the workflow solidification is of a good quality and ready for the next phase,
 - xi. **Evolutionary** - it promotes the evolution of the workflow and suggests the next aspects of the workflow that can be improved, or rather solidified,
 - xii. **Idempotent** - Each phase of the process can be repeated multiple times, we can go back (and even forth, conforming to the minimum of gate-keeping requirements)
- Considering the "Workflow-driven" nature of the solidification process, we can tweak and optimize its own meta-flow and end up with personalized solidification process that is tailored to the specific needs of the research project or research community.
- In the period of increasing human+AI symbiotic research, the solidification process in whole has (to have) one more ever-increasingly important role - to proactively engages participants in critical and creative thinking and decision-making and to keep human on the loop and ensures the transparency of the created workflows. We have already conducted a

small scale study at a workshop observing the very phenomenon and the role of the solidification process in counter-fighting it. In the following sections we will elaborate on it and the countermeasures.

In the solidification process, "*ideation*", "*taskation*" and partially "*tooling*" phases realize the role of "*operationalization*" (Pichler and Reiter, 2022) by transforming a researcher's conceptual understanding of their project into a concrete, structured, and eventually executable workflow.

To comprehend the solidification process as a whole, consider the example of a "*solidification dialogue*" between a researcher (in the dialogue with nickname "*@mPrinC*") and the AI-augmented ColaboFlow assistant (in the dialogue with nickname "*@Colabo*"), which helps with the phases in the process of solidification (see the figure (fig. 13)). The dialogue itself is conducted in the LitTerra platform even though it is implemented in the ColaboFlow framework and is, as such, agnostic of the integrating platform. The AI-augmented ColaboFlow assistant supports (i) a set of specialized *tuned prompts* for the OpenAI "ChatGPT 4o" model (apart of the current preferences, the rest of the system is agnostic of the chosen LLM model), (ii) form-like *interactive* interaction within the dialogue (like tables with the tasks list) and with (iii) an in-dialogue integrated *workflow visualization*. This helps the user to incrementally, and fluently (in a dialogical manner), digitize what is very often tacit and evasive knowledge into a final visual and explicit model. The visual model itself has two forms depending on the solidification phase the digitization process is in: **(1)** a high-level and abstract *tabular representation* of the workflow (where the user can see the flow steps and their descriptions and interact with the flow steps/tasks through checkboxes as, for example, they select which steps they want to merge - at the beginning of the (fig. 13) dialogue) and **(2)** a *workflow visualization* in the BPMN format (where the user can see the flow steps and their dependencies and interact with the flow steps/tasks through a much more advanced BPMN interface - as - at the end of the (fig. 13) dialogue), which supports much more complex forms (like branching, parallelism, encapsulation, among others) than the tabular representation.

5.1 Phases of Solidification

Below, we elaborate on each of the solidification phases and their benefits to the user and the digitization process. We explain each phase, its role, its benefits, how it contributes to the digitization process, and its outcome. Eventually, we provide a set of formal,

behavioral and AI strategies for most of the phases that are used to increase each phase's efficiency and outcome. We also present plans for future work for each phase whereby we plan to improve the respective phase's efficiency and outcome.

Later in the paper we evaluate efficiency of some of the phases through the experiments with human generated and hybrid (human+synthetic) data (sec 6).

5.1.1 Ideation

Description - in this phase, a researcher has an overall idea of the research goals and the process that should lead to implementation. They explain it in a close-to-researcher manner (so using their own language, concepts and comprehension) without a strong need to understand the underlying tasks that the workflow will eventually consist off.

Role - this phase helps users more clearly express the research idea and its various aspects. The AI-augmented ColaboFlow platform, supported with ideation-related prompts, drives the researcher in a dialogical form to a more descriptive and complete research process. It (i) extracts workflow *keywords* and (ii) suggests the missing aspects of the workflow (like missing input data, explanation of the expected outcome, description of the workflow purpose or its constraints).

Benefits - users end up with a more detailed and structured workflow description that can be used in the subsequent phases of the solidification process.

Outcome - the outcome of the ideation phase is a structured and detailed workflow description, workflow keywords, and workflow scope.

Future Work - (i) we would like to introduce workflow patterns and templates. For example, we would like to be able identify if a workflow is monolingual (and therefore sequential) or cross-lingual (and therefore parallel, with one "track" for each language). Based on the workflow type identified, we would like to be able suggest or converge to the workflow pattern that supports the identified type. We expect that by hybrid-reading (distant reading insights + close reading understanding) the workflows corpus (like SSHOM or NLP-related workflows) we can identify those workflow patterns. (ii) We also want to expand the solidification meta-flow bring in various methodologies' implementation to introduce collaboration and elevate creativity aspects in the ideation phase and, together with AI augmentation, help in brainstorming, merging alternative options from other users, and summarizing the workflow description, among others.

LitTerra

TopiChat - Flow Ideation

@mPrinC 12:35:58
Hi @colabo, I want to create a new workflow.

@Colabo 12:36:03
Great! Could you describe your workflow? Please share an overview of what tasks it involves, any datasets or events, and what you'd like the workflow to achieve. Once I have those details, I'll generate a structured flow for you.

@mPrinC 12:36:14
The workflow loads the TEI:XML document, a play from Ibsen corpora and creates a LitTerra document with only Nora's lines.

@Colabo 12:36:20
Thank you for the description! Here's the initial structured workflow based on your input. Let me know if you'd like to specify additional details, such as the exact structure of the input/output data or any specific tools/software to be used.

Extract Nora's Lines from TEI:XML
Loads the TEI:XML document, a play from Ibsen corpora and creates a LitTerra document with only Nora's lines.

- Load TEI:XML document
Loads the TEI:XML document of a play from the Ibsen corpus.
- Filter Nora's lines
Filters the lines spoken by Nora in the play.
- Create LitTerra Document
Generates a LitTerra document with only Nora's lines.

@mPrinC 12:36:44
Split the 1st task in two tasks

@Colabo 12:36:48
Here is the updated workflow with the first task split into two separate tasks:

Extract Nora's Lines from TEI:XML
Loads the TEI:XML document, a play from Ibsen corpora and creates a LitTerra document with only Nora's lines.

- Retrieve TEI:XML File
Fetches the TEI:XML file of the play from the Ibsen corpus.
- Parse TEI:XML Document
Parses the retrieved TEI:XML file into a structured document for further processing.
- Filter Nora's Lines
Extracts all lines spoken by Nora from the parsed TEI:XML document.
- Create LitTerra Document
Generates a LitTerra document with only Nora's lines.

@mPrinC 12:37:01
Merge and add icons to task titles

@Colabo 12:37:06
Here is the updated workflow with task_parse_tei_file and task_filter_nora_lines merged into a single task:

Extract Nora's Lines from TEI:XML
Loads the TEI:XML document, a play from Ibsen corpora and creates a LitTerra document with only Nora's lines.

- Retrieve TEI:XML File
Fetches the TEI:XML file of the play from the Ibsen corpus.
- Process and Filter Nora's Lines
Parses the retrieved TEI:XML file and extracts all lines spoken by Nora.
- Create LitTerra Document
Generates a LitTerra document with only Nora's lines.

@mPrinC 12:37:20
Great, thanks!

@Colabo 12:37:25
You're welcome! 🎉 If you need further assistance with refining or expanding your workflow, feel free to ask. Happy creating! 🥳 Here is the visual representation of the workflow:

Extract Nora's Lines from TEI:XML
id: id-1731726069972-qd9at1


```

graph LR
    Start((Start)) --> Retrieve[Retrieve TEI:XML File]
    Retrieve --> Process[Process and Filter Nora's Lines]
    Process --> Create[Create LitTerra Document]
    Create --> Event((Unnamed Event))
  
```

Flow

Type a command in natural language

Figure 13: Solidification dialogue between a user and the AI-augmented ColaboFlow framework assistant in the process of creation of a new workflow from its initial idea through a series of solidification phases

5.1.2 Taskation

Description - in this phase, ColaboFlow helps researchers in a "taskation" process where the researcher is guided through the process of workflow decomposition into tasks and datasets. Users can suggest their own tasks.

Role - AI-augmentation in this phase provides the researcher with the most appropriate set of tasks and datasets to use in the workflow. The researcher can interact with AI-augmentation and request it to make suggestions, add, merge, and reorganize tasks.

Benefits - The workflow is enriched with the tasks and datasets that are its foundation. The researcher is guided through the process of workflow decomposition.

Outcome - the outcome of the taskation phase is a list of tasks and datasets that forms the foundation of the workflow.

Future Work - we would like to improve the AI-augmentation suggestions based on existing workflows and datasets and their usage in similar research scenarios.

5.1.3 Health

Description - This phase evaluates workflows' structural health and completeness. The proposed concept is similar to static code analysis in programming. The tool enables the suggestion of possible improvements or the detection of potential errors as part of workflow solidification. It also proactively enhances the quality of workflow design. Keyword Matching: Check for essential keywords in descriptions to ensure that critical aspects are explicitly addressed in each workflow task. Dependency Validation: Verify that described dependencies between tasks are accurately represented and sequentially logical, reducing the risk of gaps or improper task order.

Role - this phase evaluates the outcome of the *taskation* phase and ensures that the workflow is consistent and complete. The AI-augmentation evaluates (i) the sequence of tasks against the workflow description and (ii) the tasks extracted keywords against the workflow description and its keywords. After identifying any discrepancies, It helps fixing them.

Benefits - the workflow is consistent and complete, and the researcher is guided through the process of workflow validation.

Outcome - the outcome of the consistency phase is a consistent and complete workflow.

Future Work - Structural Completeness: Evaluate if the workflow follows standard structures or templates to ensure all necessary phases are included.

5.1.4 Tooling

Description - This phase is responsible for matching the tasks in the workflow with the most appropriate tools and services that should be used for their execution. AI-augmentation is used in this phase to suggest the most appropriate tools and services for each task based on the task description and the overall workflow. It consequently depends, in a way, on the previous and following tasks as well. AI-augmentation is based on the existing workflows but primarily on the workflow that is solidified and its task description.

Role - AI-augmentation matches the tasks and their description with the list of possible tools and services that are available in the ColaboFlow framework. If matched, they are suggested. Otherwise, the AI augmentation suggests the creation of a new tool or service that should be used in the workflow.

Benefits - Through this phase, the user will get significant understanding of how they should proceed with the solidification process and start perceiving its executable perspective. AI augmentation can dramatically reduce the time needed to find the appropriate tools and services for the relevant workflow tasks. AI can also suggest and articulate the needs for new tools and services that are missing in the provided toolset.

Outcome - A list of tools and services that are matched with the tasks in the workflow. Suggestions for new tools and services that are missing in the provided toolset.

Future Work - Service Consistency (Future work): Confirm that a correct service is assigned to each task for its execution, with suggestions of the known publicly available services, based on the task description. Resource Allocation (Future work): Ensure that each task refers to concrete datasets mentioned among its resources or inputs. The datasets's "health", their availability, and whether they are outdated.

5.1.5 Schemation

Description - In this phase, we focus on (i) the schema of the datasets used in the workflow and (ii) the interfaces of the tasks that build the workflow.

Role - We want to make sure that the dataset schemas and task interfaces are consistent and complete and to provide them if they are missing for some of the tasks' input or output datasets in the workflow.

Benefits - The workflow is enriched with the datasets' schemas and the tasks' interfaces. This results in enormous benefits to the user in the further work on the given workflow; be it in the workflow's redesign, collaboration, evaluation or execution. Having all the aspects of the workflow seman-

tically annotated, both the workflow consistency and AI-augmentation components can evaluate workflow design, understand if datasets are semantically correct and expected by the tools employed by each task and suggest the necessary transformations and harmonizations of the datasets and their schemas, as appropriate.

Outcome - the workflow fully semantically annotated with the datasets' schemas and the tasks' interfaces.

Future Work - (i) Schema Completeness: all datasets are semantically annotated, (ii) Schema Correctness: all datasets are semantically correct, (iii) Datasets vs. Tools Matching: all datasets are semantically correct and expected by the tasks' tools inputs (interfaces), (iv) Schema induction: AI augmentation can induce schemas for the datasets that are missing them or extend incomplete schemas, (v) Interface induction: AI augmentation can induce interfaces for the tasks that are missing them or extend incomplete interfaces.

6 EVALUATION

Considering the reasonably poor support available for the more advanced aspects of publically available workflows, tools and datasets when it comes to their semantic descriptions (required for the full solidification process), we have decided to evaluate the solidification process and the ColaboFlow framework both through human-generated (meta-)data and through partially synthetic (meta-)data generated from human-generated (meta-)data.

SSHOM is an aggregator of 20 repository sources²⁰ that aggregates them under normalized meta-data schemas, primarily focuses on the humanities and is publicly available with open API access. We have therefore chosen its dataset for our evaluation.

There are 3 core meta-data categories that we are interested in at the moment:

- i. **workflows** - there are currently 76 workflows provided. While this is not a great number of workflows, it is sufficient for our evaluation. The workflows are described with their metadata, their tasks' metadata, and their datasets' metadata.
- ii. **tools & services** - there are currently 2436 tools and services available in the SSHOM repository.
- iii. **datasets** - there are currently 1776 datasets available in the SSHOM repository.

Each of the categories is connected with the items in other categories. For example, each workflow has

a set of tasks and each task is associated with a set of datasets and tools. This can be used to evaluate the solidification process.

6.1 Solidification evaluation and its components - Multi-Vector RAG System

As part of the solidification methodology, during the *tooling* phase (sec. 5.1.4), AI-augmentation helps user to identify (and in a sense "*autocomplete*") and suggest the most suitable tools for fulfilling each specific task of a workflow they are solidifying. This kind of an intelli-sens technology is provided through AI-augmentation component analyzing workflow's tasks and comparing them against the known database of the available (or existing) tools.

To evaluate the objective performance of this aspect of the "*tooling*" phase, we have set an experimental settings and integrated it with the functionality of the ColaboFlow framework and the Solidification component (fig. 14).

to the Multi-Vector RAG System (explained below in details). RAG preselects a wider set of relevant tools with associated descriptions, to be sent to LLM to provide a precise set of relevant tools. We have provided the evaluation code²¹

We have populated the Multi-Vector RAG System with the SSHOM dataset, primarily with tools to be able to match them against tasks. In that process we processed every relevant property of a tool to be able to match workflow task against them. In that process we had to tokenize texts and then calculate their embeddings (vector). Considering that tokenization in its standard form can truncate longer texts, resulting in an inaccurate matching, we observed the tokenization process and confirmed that only 28 of 2436*2=4872 texts were truncated and never more than 1/2 of the text was truncated. This means that the tokenization process is not a significant issue for our evaluation.

The system is evaluated on SSHOM dataset consisting of 76 workflows and 2436 tools. There are overall 551 task of which 180 reference tools which makes each third task referencing at least one tool (some of them even 5). Similarly, 50 of 76 workflows have at least one task that reference a tool.

The solidification procedure is evaluated against each workflows' step (task) that is already linked to some of these tools. The system successfully suggested 88 tools for 180 tasks, having matching rate of 49% which means that researcher should expect to

²⁰SSHOM sources: <https://marketplace-api.sshopencloud.eu/api/sources>

²¹colabogo-solidification Repository: <https://github.com/Cha-OS/colabogo-solidification>

Figure 14: ColaboFlow Solidification: Evaluation Environment

get to correct tool offered one in two times.

By using RAG, we have lowered the cost of the system, increased its speed and accuracy, all of that by introducing domain-specific knowledge and context.

The system in question is a semantic search system for discovering computational tools and workflows by understanding multiple dimensions of each resource simultaneously.

6.1.1 Purpose

Enables researchers to find relevant tools and workflows through natural language queries that match against tool descriptions, capabilities, input/output formats, and associated tags—all at once rather than searching each aspect separately.

6.1.2 Key Features

- **Multi-dimensional matching:** Searches tool names, descriptions, functionality tags, and data schemas simultaneously.
- **Workflow-aware:** Understands relationships between tools, datasets, tasks, and complete workflows.
- **Flexible discovery:** Supports queries like “Python tools for CSV analysis” that match across

multiple tool attributes.

6.1.3 Integration Value

- **Enhanced discoverability:** Researchers can find tools through varied conceptual approaches (by function, data type, methodology, or domain).
- **Workflow composition:** Facilitates building research pipelines by understanding tool compatibility and data flow requirements.
- **Reduced friction:** Eliminates the need for researchers to know exact tool names or navigate complex taxonomies.

The system serves as an intelligent intermediary between researchers’ conceptual needs (“*I need to process historical census data*”) and available computational resources, understanding both the semantic intent and technical requirements for effective tool recommendation.

6.2 Workflow Consistency Check Evaluation

A research experiment was executed on the SSHOM dataset of publicly available workflows represented with their description and the respective descriptions of each task that they are composed of, among other

relevant information. The goal of the experiment was to evaluate if the proposed tool can identify a significant amount of irregularities or unhealthy designed workflows among those considered to be consistent based on previous checks by their developers.

During the training phase of the components designated for the solidification process in ColaboFlow, the training component is fed with the SSHOM JSON schema description, allowing it to access and understand the workflows' structure. For each workflow, we extract (i) a set of workflow description keywords, (ii) *taskKeywords* - a set of keywords for each workflow's task, (iii) *matchedWorkflowKeywordsWithTaskText* - a set of workflow keywords that are matched with tasks label and description, (iv) *matchedWorkflowKeywordsWithTaskKeywords* - a set of workflow keywords that are matched with *taskKeywords*.

Using the data provided, workflow consistency is evaluated. Tasks are executed in search for the identified keywords.

non-utilized workflow keywords - the keywords missing from any of the workflow's tasks' descriptions are recognized as an indication of the tasks' not fulfilling the workflow's objectives correctly.

non-utilized task keywords - the task keywords missing from the workflow's description are recognized as an indication of the workflow description not correctly fulfilling the workflow's tasks' objectives.

See figure (fig. 15) to better understand the regular balance between the number of keywords per task and their deviation. The figure (fig. 17) reflects the distribution of the keyword count across all workflows in an aggregated form and informs the components in the *Consistency* phase how to "shape" the tasks' description "reverse engineered" from the number of keywords they produce and would help the AI augmentation to provide more accurate suggestions and help the user to articulate the workflow description and tasks' description more accurately according to the expected norms.

Results of the experiment show the benefit of the Workflow Consistency Check in the maintenance support and of health checks of the public workflow repositories in addition to individual management.

7 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented workflows in DH as a foundation of reproducible research together with the ColaboFlow framework and Bukvik and LitTerra platforms that support workflow methodology, reproducible research and the "human-on-the-loop" principle. We have focused on the key features of the

platform that contribute to both of these aspects. We have presented aspects of reproducible research, its challenges and benefits and the ways increase a DH researcher's incentive to adopt them. In addition to conventional motivators of reproducible research, we have addressed the process of "solidification", which transforms the declarative creative process (or work) into a solid, executable, and reproducible workflow. We have augmented solidification methodology with *responsible* AI-augmentation strategies. We have, further, evaluated the solidification process and the ColaboFlow framework through both human-generated data and partially synthetic data generated from human-generated data.

8 FUTURE WORK

This paper presents our work and contribution to reproducible research and workflows in DH. Further research would focus on improving the generative tasks of the solidification process and accompanying matching tasks intended to improve the resulting workflows. We would like to pay special attention to providing full support of workflow templates and workflow-digitization workflows or, in other words, to designing workflows that should drive a scholar's process of digitizing their research work into workflows. Finally, the challenge of keeping a human-on-the-loop approach and providing a clear balance, engagement, and role of the AI between augmenting humans and harming users in the long term is an open and challenging research question that we would like to address in our future work. This would primarily focus on work with CoPs (Communities of Practice), capturing their working procedures and impact of AI augmentation on their work. This would give us initial insights and mechanisms and *gatekeepers* for keeping AI responsible and supportive of the human-on-the-loop principles.

Acknowledgement - We want to thank to ChaOS NGO, LitTerra Foundation, Inverudio, SAS, and University of Oslo for providing the support for conducting the research.

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Figure 15: Task Description Balance Across Workflows represented individually for each workflow

Figure 16: Keyword distribution in the SSHOM dataset of workflows (aggregated across all workflows)

Figure 17: Keyword count distribution (aggregated across all workflows)

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